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Abstract: Shortening the juvenile period (JP) is one of the main strategies to increase the efficiency of olive breeding programs due to the long generation time of this species. Seedling vigor has been reported to be negatively associated to the length of the JP. In the present work we analyzed the influence of the female genitor on the length of the JP of olive seedlings, their vigor (plant height and trunk diameter), and the relationship between seedling vigor and JP using 3650 seedlings from 10 female genitors evaluated over 14 years. Overall, the length of the JP significantly varied for the female genitor and year of germination. Female genitors evaluated were classified into three groups according to the length of the JP of their progeny, as follows: short ('Arbequina' and 'UCI 7-34'); medium ('Lechín de Sevilla', 'Manzanilla de Sevilla', 'Picual', 'UCI 11-28' and 'Zaity'); and long JP ('Frantoio', 'Memecik' and 'UCI 10-30'). Vigor, measured as the height of the seedling at planting, was significantly correlated ($P < 0.001$) with the length of the JP for all progenies except for those of 'Lechín de Sevilla', 'Memecik' and 'UCI 10-30' because most of their seedlings did not flower during the studied period. The highest proportion of flowering plants was obtained when the height of the plants was from 126 to 150 cm at planting. In addition, flowering, measured as presence or absence of flowers, was significantly related to the plant height according to a logistic regression. Nevertheless, for each female genitor, the inflection point of the curve (height at which 50% of the seedlings flowered) presented different values, suggesting that height selection thresholds should be specific for each female genitor.

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Monday, January 28, 2013

Dear Sir.

Please find enclosed a manuscript entitled: "Female genital effect on the juvenile period of olive seedlings" which I am submitting for exclusive consideration of publication as an article in *Scientia Horticulturae*.

The paper reinforces the strategy of forcing of olive seedling growth to shorten their Juvenile Period using specific female genitors. As such this paper should be of interest to a broad readership including those interested in olive tree or tree breeding.

Thank you for your consideration of my work! Please address all correspondence concerning this manuscript to me at My Research Center and feel free to correspond with me by e-mail (jmoral@ias.csic.es).

Sincerely

Juan Moral

Highlights

- We studied the female genitor effect on the earliness of bearing of its progeny in an olive-breeding program.
- We evaluated 3650 seedlings from 10 female genitors over 14 years.
- The length of the JP varied greatly for the female genitor and year of germination.
- In general, vigor was significantly correlated with the Juvenile Period
- Flowering was significantly related to the plant height according to a logistic regression.
- Height selection thresholds should be specific for each female genitor.

Female genitor effect on the juvenile period of olive seedlings

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ABSTRACT

Shortening the juvenile period (JP) is one of the main strategies to increase the efficiency of olive breeding programs due to the long generation time of this species. Seedling vigor has been reported to be negatively associated to the length of the JP. In the present work we analyzed the influence of the female genitor on the length of the JP of olive seedlings, their vigor (plant height and trunk diameter), and the relationship between seedling vigor and JP using 3650 seedlings from 10 female genitors evaluated over 14 years. Overall, the length of the JP significantly varied for the female genitor and year of germination. Female genitors evaluated were classified into three groups according to the length of the JP of their progeny, as follows: short ('Arbequina' and 'UCI 7-34'); medium ('Lechín de Sevilla', 'Manzanilla de Sevilla', 'Picual', 'UCI 11-28' and 'Zaity'); and long JP ('Frantoio', 'Memecik' and 'UCI 10-30'). Vigor, measured as the height of the seedling at planting, was significantly correlated ($P < 0.001$) with the length of the JP for all progenies except for those of 'Lechín de Sevilla', 'Memecik' and 'UCI 10-30' because most of their seedlings did not flower during the studied period. The highest proportion of flowering plants was obtained when the height of the plants was from 126 to 150 cm at planting. In addition, flowering, measured as presence or absence of flowers, was significantly related to the plant height according to a logistic regression. Nevertheless, for each female genitor, the inflection point of the

curve (height at which 50% of the seedlings flowered) presented different values, suggesting that height selection thresholds should be specific for each female genitor.

Keywords: *Olea europaea*, juvenile phase, vigor, selection, breeding.

1. Introduction

The long time between seed germination and the first flowering, called the Juvenile Period (JP), has been the main obstacle in cross-breeding programs for fruit crops (Janick and Moore, 1996). This period may be extremely long in olive (*Olea europaea* L.), lasting up to 15-20 years in trees growing under natural conditions (Fontanazza and Baldoni, 1990; Rugini, 1990; Bellini et al 2002). The selection of new cultivars is based on the assessment of thousands of seedlings after they have reached the adult stage and are able to flower and produce fruit and oil for evaluation (Rallo 1995; Rallo et al., 2011). The length of the JP is influenced by both environmental and genetic factors (Hackett, 1985) and the shortening of JP in the seedlings of several fruit species has been possible by forcing their growth under optimal conditions (Aldwinckle, 1975; Zimmerman, 1977). This general technique was applied to olive, allowing reduce the JP up to 2-4 years, whereby seedlings were grown in a greenhouse under continuous light at an average temperature of 22°C. Afterwards, they were planted in an open field under drip fertigation, with their canopy trained at a height of 160 cm (Santos-Antunes et al., 2005). Moreno-Alías et al. (2010) observed short JP on seedlings with canopies trained at 100-130 cm. Despite this outstanding reduction in JP, this developmental stage remains a barrier for obtaining new cultivars because a minimum of two years are necessary to obtain adult plants.

Plant vigor, which is measured as plant height and trunk diameter, is positively associated with a short JP (Pritsa et al., 2003; De la Rosa et al., 2006; Rallo et al., 2008). This relationship has allowed the development of early negative selection criteria based on seedling vigor measured before planting (De la Rosa et al., 2006; Rallo et al., 2008). Those criteria allowed the elimination of plants with lower height and trunk diameter, most of them likely having a long juvenile period and thus being undesirable for the breeding selection process. Previous works, based on the three cultivars initially used as genitors on the olive breeding program of Córdoba ('Arbequina', 'Frantoio' and 'Picual'), indicated that female genitors might have a significant influence on the length of the juvenile period of their seedlings (Santos-Antunes et al., 2005). The present study is aimed to evaluate the influence of additional genitors, subsequently used in this breeding program, on the vigor and JP of their seedlings. Moreover, we explore the critical values of plant height and stem diameter that could be used as proxies of the length of JP. A preliminary report of this study has been published (Moral et al., 2011).

2. Materials and methods

2.1 Plant material

The length of JP of 3381 seedlings, coming from 10 olive cultivars used as the female genitors, was evaluated within the framework of the Join Olive Breeding Program of the University of Córdoba - IFAPA (Andalusian Institute for Agricultural Research), Spain. All seedlings were obtained either by controlled crosses or by open pollinations in 1992, 1993, 1994, 1998, 1999 and 2001. Each year of germination, three to five of the following widely grown cultivars were chosen as the female genitors: ‘Arbequina’, ‘Frantoio’, ‘Lechín de Sevilla’, ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Memecik’, ‘Picual’ and ‘Zaity’ (Table 1). These cultivars show different agronomic characteristics and are considered to be native from Spain, with the exception of ‘Frantoio’, ‘Memecik’ and ‘Zaity’, which are from Italy, Turkey and Syria, respectively (Barranco et al., 2000). The breeding selections ‘UCI 7-34’ (‘Picual’ ♀ × ‘Arbequina’ ♂), ‘UCI 10-30’ (‘Frantoio’ ♀ × ‘Picual’ ♂) and ‘UCI 11-28’ (‘Picual’ ♀ × ‘Arbequina’ ♂), which were obtained in the breeding program above mentioned, were also included in this study. In addition, 269 seedlings obtained from crosses performed in 2004 were used to study the relationship between vigor and length of the JP (Table 2).

The seeds from the different crossings were collected in the autumn, extracted from the fruits, chilled at 14°C and subsequently germinated following the protocol described by Santos-Antunes et al. (2005). The germinated seedlings were transplanted to 3 L pots and placed in a greenhouse where they were grown with drip fertigation, controlled temperature (22°C on average) and continuous light provided by sodium lamps. The seedlings germinated in 1992, 1993, 1994, 1998 and 1999 were planted in the field at 4 × 1.5 m spacing two years after germination, and their crown was trained at a height of 160 cm. The plants germinated in 2001 and 2004 were also planted at 4 × 1.5 m spacing, and the crown was established at a height of 100-130 cm. All the plants were planted in different plots located at the “Alameda del Obispo” Center of the IFAPA in Córdoba, southern Spain (37.51°N, 4.80°W, elevation of 110 m). The soil of the orchard was classified as Typic Xero Fluvent of sandy-loam texture, and the climatic conditions were typical of the Mediterranean region, with a mean annual precipitation of 620 mm and a marked summer drought (< 30 mm of rain from June through September). Pest control, soil fertilization and soil management practices were conducted in accordance with regional commercial practices.

2.2 Data records

Flowering was visually evaluated in each seedling during the spring for 3 to 6 years after germination (Table 1). The occurrence of first flowering in a given seedling was associated to phase change from juvenile to adult as considered in previous works (Santos-Antunes et al., 2005).

The plant height and stem diameter at 1 m from the ground were measured on the 738 and 633 seedlings germinated during 1998 and 2001 respectively; before they were transplanted to the field. Additionally, the same vigor parameters were measured under field conditions during the springs of the 5th year after germination (3st years growing in field conditions) on the seedlings obtained in 1998 and 2004.

2.3 Statistical analysis

The influence of the female genitor on the length of JP was measured using flowering curves estimated by the Kaplan-Meier method (1958) in which flowering (0 = absence or 1 = presence of inflorescences) was used as the event variable and the years since germination were used as the time variable. Moreover, the Kaplan-Meier percentiles (i.e., 10, 25, 50, 75 and 90%) were calculated. The effect of the female genitor on the length of JP was studied using a Longrank test at $P = 0.05$. The effect of the female genitor on the vigor parameters at plantation time was analyzed using the Kruskal-Wallis one-way nonparametric test, and the means were compared according to Dunn's test at $P = 0.05$ (seedlings germinated in 1998 and 2001). Because the number of seedlings from each cross was very unbalanced and due to the occurrence of illicit pollination caused by airborne pollen, the effect of the male genitor was not studied.

To assess the possible relationship between vigor and the length of JP of the progeny of each cultivar at 5th year after germination (progenies obtained in 1998 and 2004), a logistic regression was performed considering the significance of independent and dependent variables of the regression (plant height and flowering, respectively) and the pattern of the residuals. The inflection point (height at which 50% of the seedlings flowered) of each cultivar was calculated by numerical integration. The relationship between the stem diameter and the height of the progeny seedling was studied using linear regression. This latter analysis was performed considering the significance of the regression, coefficient of determination (R^2), coefficient of determination adjusted for degrees of freedom (Ra^2) and pattern of residuals. Lastly, the relationship between the

height of the plants before transplanting and the length of JP was studied using a nonparametric Spearman Rank Correlation (progenies obtained in 1998 and 2001). For this, a time scale of the first flowering [from 4 (flowering in the 4th year after germination) to 7 (no flowering at 6 years after germination)] was used. The data from all the experiments were analyzed using Statistix 9 (Analytical Software, Tallahassee, FL).

3. Results

Female genitors and year of germination greatly influenced on the length of JP of the seedlings (Fig. 1; Table 1). Thus, the percentage of seedlings of ‘Arbequina’ and ‘Picual’ that flowered during the first 5 years after planting varied greatly among the years of germinations: i) more than 80% for both genitors in the progenies germinated in 1992, 1993 and 1994; ii) 79 (‘Arbequina’) and 48% (‘Picual’) in the progenies germinated in 1998; and iii) approximately 65 (‘Arbequina’) and 55% (‘Picual’) in the progenies germinated 1999 and 2001, respectively.

Due to this high variation among the years of germination and to isolate the effects of the genitors, we grouped the different years of germination of seedlings into homogeneous groups, with no significant differences among them and growing under similar conditions (crown height and distance between olives in the field). Therefore, the seedlings germinated in 1992, 1993 and 1994 were grouped together, and the remaining of seedlings (1998, 1999 and 2001) were studied independently.

3.1. Influence of genitor on the length of JP and vigor of the seedlings

In seedlings germinated in 1992, 1993 and 1994, the length of the JP for the progeny of ‘Arbequina’ was the shortest, followed by ‘Picual’ and ‘Frantoio’, showing significant differences among them (Longrank test, $P < 0.0001$; Table 1). According to Kaplan-Meier’s percentiles, 50% of the seedlings (50th percentile) of ‘Arbequina’ and ‘Picual’ flowered during the first 4 years after germination. In contrast, the progeny of ‘Frantoio’ required two additional years to attain the same percentage of flowering.

In seedlings germinated in 1998, the progeny of ‘Arbequina’ and ‘UCI 7-34’ showed a significantly ($P < 0.05$) shorter JP than the progeny of ‘Lechín de Sevilla’, ‘Picual’ and ‘UCI 10-30’, which did not present significant differences among them ($P > 0.05$). The time required to reach the 10th percentile of flowering plants highlighted

the differences between these two groups. In fact, the progeny of ‘Arbequina’ and ‘UCI 7-34’ only required 4 years to reach this percentile, whereas those of ‘Picual’, ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ and ‘UCI 10-30’ required 4.4, 5 and 5.4 years, respectively (Table 1).

In seedlings germinated in 1999, the progeny of ‘Arbequina’ and ‘Memecik’ showed the shortest and longest JP length, respectively ($P < 0.05$). The progeny of ‘Picual’, ‘UCI 11-28’ and ‘Zaity’ presented an intermediate JP length, without significant differences among them ($P > 0.05$). The 25th percentile clearly evidenced the short JP of the progeny of ‘Arbequina’, which required 4 years to reach this percentile, whereas the remaining cultivars required 5 years. In last case (2001), the JP length and the Kaplan-Meier’s percentiles were not influenced by any female cultivar (Table 1).

In seedlings germinated in 1998, the average height of the seedlings before plantation varied (Dunn’s test, $P < 0.05$) depending on the female genitor, as follows: ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ (131 cm) > ‘Picual’ (125 cm) = ‘Arbequina’ (122 cm) > ‘UCI 7-34’ (118 cm) = ‘UCI 10-30’ (108 cm). The seedlings of ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ and ‘UCI 10-30’ also showed the thickest and thinnest trunk diameter, respectively. However, the remaining progeny did not show clear differences among them. Likewise those germinated in 2001, the female significantly (Dunn’s test, $P < 0.05$) affected vigor parameters of seedlings. Thus, the seedlings formed three groups, being the seedlings from ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’ (165 cm) and ‘Picual’ (105 cm) the most and less vigorous, respectively. The seedlings from ‘Arbequina’ (160 cm) showed an intermediate vigor.

The female genitor also affected the height of the progeny under field conditions at the 5th year after germination (Dunn’s test, $P < 0.05$). In seedlings germinated in 1998, those of ‘UCI 7-34’ and ‘UCI 10-30’ showed the highest and lowest vigor, respectively, whereas the other progeny were characterized by an intermediate vigor. The progeny obtained in 2004 could be classified according to their vigor, as follows: ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’ > ‘Picual’ > ‘Arbequina’.

3.2. Vigor as a proxy of a short JP

In all studied cases, the plant height and trunk diameter were highly correlated ($R^2 > 0.453$ and $P < 0.0001$) both before plantation and in the field at 5 years after germination. Therefore, both measurements were taken into account to characterize the

vigor of the plants.

No seedlings germinated during 1998 with a height lower than 75 cm at planting flowered during the first 5 years. The mean and standard deviation (SD) of height of this progeny at plantation time were 123 ± 28 cm. The frequency (%) of seedlings that flowered in the 4th year after germination increased linearly (from 0 to 25%) for increasing plant height from 75 to 175 cm. When we studied the accumulated frequency (%) of the seedlings that flowered during the first 6 years, this frequency increased with increasing plant height until it reached a maximum of 126-150 cm; the frequency remained constant thereafter, i.e., when the seedlings were taller than 150 cm (Fig. 2A).

In seedlings germinated in 2001, only 11 of them (around 2%) flowered during the first 5 years. Thus, no seedlings with a height lower than 147 cm at planting flowered during this period. The height and SD of this progeny at plantation time were 160 ± 34 cm. The number of seedling that flowered at 5th or 6th years after germination was linearly related with the average height of seedlings from 75 to 175 cm and it decreased to seedling height > 175 cm (Fig. 2B).

The vigor parameters at plantation time (seedlings germinated in 1998 and 2001) were positively (Spearman rank test; $P < 0.05$) correlated with a short JP in the progeny of 'Arbequina', 'Picual', 'Manzanilla de Sevilla' and 'UCI 7-34'. In contrast, this correlation was not observed among the seedlings of 'Lechín de Sevilla' and 'UCI 10-30', which exhibited longer JPs (Spearman rank test; $P > 0.05$).

The relationship between flowering and plant height measured in the 5th year after germination was well described by a logistic model, with the exception of the progeny of 'UCI 10-30', which barely flowered during this year (Table 2). The inflection point (height at which 50% of the seedlings flowered) of the curve was strongly influenced by the female genitor. In seedlings germinated in 1998, the largest difference was found between the progeny of 'Arbequina' (303 cm) and 'Lechín de Sevilla' (328 cm). In seedlings obtained in 2004, the inflection point of the progeny of 'Arbequina' and 'Picual' decreased markedly compared to the previous germination year (1998), decreasing from 303 to 169 and from 314 to 205 cm, respectively. In this case (2004), the progeny of 'Manzanilla de Sevilla' showed the highest inflection point (211 cm), confirming the high vigor transmitted by this cultivar to their seedlings.

4. Discussion

In several fruit crops, it has been reported the influence of the genitors on the length of the JP of their seedlings (Hansche, 1986; Visser, 1970, 1976; Bell and Zimmerman, 1990). However, this effect and the pattern by which seedlings progressively overcome JP in a long-term study have rarely been investigated in olive (Santos-Antunes et al., 2005; De la Rosa et al., 2006; Rallo et al., 2008). Focusing on this goal, we evaluated the influence of 10 female genitors on the length of JP in 3381 seedlings of an olive breeding program conducted over the course of 14 years. Moreover, our aim was to determine whether vigor could be considered an efficient early selection criterion to predict a short JP.

In general, the JP length of the progeny varied greatly depending on the genitor, in agreement with previous observations (Santos-Antunes et al., 2005; De la Rosa et al., 2006; Rallo et al., 2008). In our case, the year of germination also had an important effect on the length of JP. However, the genitors that consistently transmitted a short JP, such as ‘Arbequina’, did so independently of the year of germination. This characteristic, together with other desirable agronomic traits, such as high and stable yield, make ‘Arbequina’ a very suitable genitor for breeding programs (Rallo et al., 2011).

Based on the entire data, we classified the genitors with regard to the JP length of their progeny into three groups: short (‘Arbequina’ and ‘UCI 7-34’); medium (‘Lechín de Sevilla’, ‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’, ‘Picual’, ‘UCI 11-28’ and ‘Zaity’); and long JP (‘Frantoio’, ‘Memecik’ and ‘UCI 10-30’). It is interesting to note that ‘UCI 7-34’ (a descendant of ‘Arbequina’) and ‘UCI 10-30’ (a descendant of ‘Frantoio’) had similar effects with regard to their progeny’s JP length as their parents, conferring a short and long JP, respectively.

Because olive cultivars are vegetatively propagated, rooted cuttings exhibit an unproductive period whose length is variable depending on the cultivar. As previously reported by Santos-Antunes et al. (2005), the length of the JP in progeny was related to the length of the unproductive period of their parents. For instance, ‘Arbequina’ and ‘UCI 7-34’ shows a shorter unproductive period than ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ and ‘Picual’,

which have unproductive periods shorter than ‘Frantoio’ and ‘UCI 10-30’ (Del Río and García-Fernández, 2001; Del Río et al., 2005; León et al. 2007). Notably, these cultivars were ranked in the same order with regard to the JP length of their progeny.

The year of germination also affected the length of JP of the seedlings independently of the female genitor. Figure 1 highlights the large variability in the JP of the progeny of the same female genitor among years of germination, and the observations could be due to three main reasons. i) The male genitors used in the breeding program were different each year. Undoubtedly, the effect of the male genitor is quite important and may account for a high proportion of the variation observed among the years. However, this contribution was not evaluated because the number of seedlings coming from each crossing was unbalance and sometimes scarce to get robust statistical results. Besides, the possible illicit pollination might lead to inaccurate results about the effect of the putative cultivar used as the male genitor. ii) There was variability among the soils of the plots where the seedlings were planted and different climatic conditions among the years. iii) The management of progenies was different for the progenies germinated in different years (See Material and Methods). It is noteworthy that in our study there was an inverse correlation between seedling vigor and short JP for whole data. This correlation has been previously reported in apple (Visser, 1970) and pear (Zimmerman, 1977). It has also been previously observed in olive but with a lower number crossing and samples (Santos-Antunes et al., 2005; De la Rosa et al., 2006; Rallo et al., 2008). Our results confirm this general correlation through the most extensive evaluation of JP conducted in olive to date. Moreover, we also observed an absence of this correlation in the progeny of ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ and ‘UCI 10-30’ because most of their seedlings (> 60%) did not flower during the period established of the study. Similarly, Pritsa et al. (2003) did not find a correlation between vigor and first flowering of seedlings from ‘Kalamon’, ‘Manzanillo’ and ‘Chaldikis’ that are considered to have high vigor.

In seedlings germinated in 1998, no plant shorter than 75 cm at the time of transplant flowered before 5 years after germination. This threshold height was 147 cm on the seedlings germinated in 2001. These results are in agreement with previous reports (De la Rosa et al., 2006; Rallo et al., 2008). Actually, when the height of the plants was approximately 126-150 cm, the frequency of plants with a short JP was at a maximum, in agreement with Moreno-Alias et al (2010). This finding involves

important and applied consequences for breeding because it will be helpful to shorten the time of selection for earliness of bearing. This early selection will reduce the economical costs derived from the maintenance of the plants and guarantee a short JP in the progeny.

Although we observed a general negative correlation between length of JP and plant vigor, it clearly depended on the female genitor. For instance, the progeny of ‘Lechín de Sevilla’ was the most vigorous but displayed besides ‘UCI 10-30’ the longest JPs of the progenies germinated in 1998 (Table 1). Nevertheless, the most vigorous plants of this progeny were those that showed the shortest JP. Therefore, to select for earliness of bearing, we should select genitors transmitting a short JP, and, subsequently, choose the most vigorous plants within the progeny of these genitors.

Previous reports related vigor and length of the JP. However, this is the first time that the length of the JP has been found correlated with plant height according to a logistic regression. The inflection point (height at which 50% of the seedlings flowered) of the logistic curves showed different values depending on the female parent, suggesting a critical plant height for flowering depending on the genitor, as has been reported in other fruit crops (Janick and Moore 1996). The progeny germinating in 1998 showed higher inflection points than those germinating in 2004 because the crown of the latter was trained approximately 60 cm lower than in 1998. It is interesting to note that the effect of height is related to the existence of a juvenility cone, which ultimately determines flowering (Moreno-Alías et al., 2010).

In conclusion, the female genitor clearly affected the vigor of the seedlings, though there was an influence of the year that should be taken into account. The survival analysis applied to seedling flowering over the years allowed us to compare the JP of the progeny for the duration of the study, which is more complete than studies in which the progeny were compared only for a specific year (León et al., 2007). These results reinforce the strategy of and adequate choose of the genitors in order to increase the proportion of seedlings with short JP able to be selected for subsequent steps of the breeding process.

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LEGENDS TO THE FIGURES

Figure 1. Frequency of flowering for the progeny of different olive cultivars germinated on 6 different years.

Figure 2. Accumulated frequency of the flowering of olive seedlings germinated in 1998 (**A**) and 2001(**B**), according to their height at planting.

Table 1. Influence of different female genitors on the time (years) required for their progeny to flower. The flowering percentiles (10, 25, 50, 75 or 90%) are expressed per genitor and year of germination.

Year of Germination ^a	Time of Measure (years)	Female genitor ^b	No. of seedlings	Homogeneous groups ^c	Flowering Percentiles (%) ^d				
					10	25	50	75	90
1992/93/94	3, 4, 5, 6	‘Arbequina’	297	A	3	4	4	5	5
		‘Frantoio’	212	C	4	5	6	>6	>6
		‘Picual’	239	B	4	4	4	5	6
1998	4, 5, 6	‘Arbequina’	420	A	4	6	>6	>6	>6
		‘Lechín de Sevilla’	98	B	5	6	>6	>6	>6
		‘Picual’	134	B	4.4	6	>6	>6	>6
		‘UCI 7-34’	53	A	4	5	6	>6	>6
		‘UCI 10-30’	34	B	5.4	>6	>6	>6	>6
1999	3, 4, 5	‘Arbequina’	391	A	4	4	5	>5	>5
		‘Memecik’	46	C	5	5	>5	>5	>5
		‘Picual’	214	B	4	5	5	>5	>5
		‘UCI 11-28’	38	B	4	5	5	>5	>5
		‘Zaity’	86	B	5	5	5	>5	>5
2001	3, 4, 5,	‘Arbequina’	458	A	4	5	5	>5	>5
		‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’	412	A	4.2	5	5	>5	>5
		‘Picual’	249	A	4	5	5	>5	>5
Total			3381						

^aHeight of the crown: 1992, 1993, 1994, 1998 and 1999 160 cm; 2001 100-130cm.

^bBreeding selections: 'UCI 7-34' ('Picual' ♀ × 'Arbequina' ♂), 'UCI 10-30' ('Frantoio' ♀ × 'Picual' ♂) and 'UCI 11-28' ('Picual' ♀ × 'Arbequina' ♂).

^cGroups with the same letter are not significantly different according to the Longrank test at $P = 0.05$.

^dKaplan-Meier percentiles.

Table 2. Relationship between plant height (cm) and flowering for the progeny of different olive cultivars used as the female genitor at 5th after germination

Year of germination Female genitor	No. of seedlings	Logistic Curve Parameters		Proportion of correctly classified data ^b	Inflection point (cm) ^c
		Constant (<i>P</i>)	Height (<i>P</i>)		
1998					
‘Arbequina’	420	-6.9464 (< 0.0001)	0.0229 (< 0.0001)	0.764	303
‘Lechín de Sevilla’	98	-7.5630 (0.0007)	0.0231 (0.0087)	0.888	328
‘Picual’	134	-7.2894 (< 0.0001)	0.0232 (0.0001)	0.806	314
‘UCI 7-34’	34	-14.1788 (0.0009)	0.0509 (0.0013)	0.774	278
‘UCI 10-30’	53	-5.1839 (0.04)	0.0136 (0.2025)	0.822	382
2004					
‘Arbequina’	92	-7.6451 (0.0021)	0.04532 (0.0004)	0.815	169
‘Manzanilla de Sevilla’	89	-8.8001 (0.0002)	0.04174 (0.0001)	0.753	211
‘Picual’	88	-7.4185 (< 0.0001)	0.03618 (< 0.0001)	0.751	205

^aBreeding selections: ‘UCI 7-34’ (‘Picual’ ♀ × ‘Arbequina’ ♂), ‘UCI 10-30’ (‘Frantoio’ ♀ × ‘Picual’ ♂) and ‘UCI 11-28’ (‘Picual’ ♀ × ‘Arbequina’ ♂).

^bProportion of correctly classified olive trees (with or without flowering) by the logistic model.

^cThe inflection point (height at which 50% of the seedlings flowered) was calculated by numerical integration.

Year of seed germination

Figure 2